

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterizations of some copper(II) complexes containing a 15 membered pentaaza (N_5) bis(macrocyclic) ligands

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Abstract : Copper(II) complexes of types $[(ML)_2R_1]X_4$ and $[(ML)_2R_2]Y_4$ [$M = Cu^{II}$; $L = 1,1'$ -diphenyl- and $1,1'$ -diphenylmethane-bis(1,3,7,10,14-pentaazacyclopentadeca-7,10-diene); $R_1 = (C_6H_4NH_2)_2$, $R_2 = (C_6H_4NH_2)_2CH_2$; $X = Cl^-$, CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- and $Y = ClO_4^-$] were synthesized and characterized by microanalytical, spectroscopic and other physicochemical results.

Keywords : Copper(II) complexes, tetradentate macrocycle, syntheses, spectral studies.

Introduction

The field of macrocyclic chemistry of metals is developing very rapidly because of its applications and importance in the area of coordination chemistry. Structural factors such as ligand rigidity, the types of donor atoms and their disposition have shown to play significant roles in determining the binding features of macrocyclic ligands toward metal cations. The development of the field of bioinorganic chemistry has been another important factor in spurring the growth of macrocyclic compounds. The chemical properties of macrocyclic complexes can be tuned to force metal ions to adopt unusual coordination geometry^{1,2}. Transition metal macrocyclic complexes have received much attention as an active part of metalloenzymes and as biomimic model compounds. It is due to their resemblance with natural proteins like hemerythrin and enzymes. The chemistry of macrocyclic compounds in particular is also important due to their catalytic and biological applications.

The preparation of bis(macrocyclic) nitrogen donor ligands with binucleating properties towards transition metals has recently attracted much attention, and a variety of systems of this type have been reported^{3,4}. Bis(cyclams) appear to be better electrocatalysts than the corresponding mononuclear species^{5,6}. The thermodynamic and kinetic inertness of transition metal complexes

of poly azamacrocyclic ligands show significant industrial application⁷⁻¹⁰. In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of new bis(macrocyclic) binuclear copper(II) complexes of 1,1'-diphenyl- and 1,1'-diphenylmethane-bis(1,3,7,10,14-pentaazacyclopentadeca-7,10-diene), $[(Cu(15)aneN_5)_2RCl_4]$, $[(Cu(15)aneN_5)_2R(NO_3)_4]$, $[(Cu(15)aneN_5)_2(CH_3COO)_4]$, $[(Cu(15)aneN_5)_2R](ClO_4)_4$. These binuclear complexes were prepared by the template condensation of the appropriate nitrogen-nitrogen linker formaldehyde, 1,3-diaminopropane, copper(II) salts and glyoxal in 1 : 4 : 4 : 2 : 2 molar ratios (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

All the complexes are synthesized by the template method. On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes were found to have the composition as shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMF solution correspond to their non electrolytic nature for $[(ML)_2R_1]X_4$ [where $X = Cl^-$, CH_3COO^- , NO_3^-] and 1 : 4 electrolytes for $[(ML)_2R_2]Y_4$ [where $Y = ClO_4^-$]. Thus the complexes may be formulated as $[(ML)_2R_1]X_4$, $[(ML)_2R_2]Y_4$ (where $M = copper(II)$ and $L = ligand$ (Table 1). The higher melting point of the complexes suggests the thermal stability of complexes.

Scheme 1. Preparation of metal complexes by template method.

IR spectra of the ligands and complexes :

The IR spectrum of the ligand does not exhibit any band corresponding to a free primary diamine and keto group⁹. The vibration due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ skeletal is present at 1407 cm^{-1} . The strong band at 1529 cm^{-1} usually due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ group. A band appearing at 1597 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric or asymmetric $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibration. On complexation, the shifting of the position of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ bands towards the lower side indicates coordination through the nitrogen atoms of the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ groups.

IR spectra of nitrate and acetato complexes :

The IR spectra of nitrate complexes of copper(II) display medium intensity bands in the region at $1425\text{--}1434$, $1304\text{--}1322$ and $910\text{--}1003\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This suggests the coordinated¹¹ behaviour of all nitrate groups with the centrally located copper(II) metal ions in a unidentate fashion.

The IR spectra of acetate complexes show bands in the region $1560\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $1380\text{--}1406\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$. The difference between these two bands $\Delta = 180\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which suggests that the acetate group is coordinated to the copper ion as a unidentate manner.

IR spectra of perchlorate complexes show bands at 1165 , 1055 and 938 cm^{-1} corresponding to uncoordinated behaviour¹¹.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moment values of copper(II) complexes of chloride, acetate and nitrate lie in the $1.92\text{--}2.02\text{ B.M.}$ range corresponding to one unpaired electron (Table 1). Electronic spectrum of the copper complexes displays band in range $9975\text{--}10992$, $14574\text{--}18621$, $20856\text{--}28571\text{ cm}^{-1}$. First two bands may be assigned to the transitions : ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) (ν_1), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$) (ν_2) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$) (ν_3).

The magnetic moment value of copper(II) perchlorate complexes were found to be 1.93 and 2.00 B.M. respectively¹²⁻¹⁵ (Table 1). The electronic spectra of these complexes display band in range $15873\text{--}16949$, $21276\text{--}22727\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands corresponds to the transition : ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) (ν_1), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$) (ν_2) respectively¹⁶.

The EPR spectra of copper(II) complexes were recorded on X band at frequency 9.1 GHz under the magnetic strength 3400 G scan rate 2000 at room temperature as polycrystalline sample and in DMF solution at liquid nitrogen temperature 'LNT'. Polycrystalline spectra show a well resolved anisotropic broad signal. The analysis of spectra give $g_{\parallel} = 2.4628\text{--}2.5201$ and $g_{\perp} = 1.9785\text{--}2.0255$ (Tables 2a, 2b). The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ observed for the complexes indicates that the unpaired electron is localized in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the copper(II) ion and spectral features are characteristic for the axial symmetry. Tetragonally elongated geometry are thus confirmed for the copper(II) complexes¹⁷. In DMF solutions EPR spectra show same features as polycrystalline.

Note

Table 1. Molar conductance, elemental analysis data, magnetic moment and electronic spectra of the complexes

Complexes	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})
	Cu	C	H	N		
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ Cl ₄	15.62	48.60	4.43	15.46	1.96	9827, 14134, 18652
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ Cl ₄]	(14.65)	(48.61)	(4.13)	(15.42)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ Cl ₄	14.64	48.62	4.40	16.45	2.02	11213, 15620, 19811
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ Cl ₄]	(14.15)	(48.73)	(4.48)	(16.38)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ (NO ₃) ₄	14.65	47.72	5.82	15.73	2.01	9756, 14234, 18876
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (NO ₃) ₄]	(14.85)	(48.67)	(5.15)	(15.67)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	13.65	47.27	4.44	13.25	1.97	10298, 15567, 19534
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (NO ₃) ₄]	(13.15)	(47.14)	(4.18)	(13.39)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	13.58	46.35	5.28	13.87	1.92	10987, 14897, 18988
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄]	(13.40)	(46.23)	(5.35)	(13.29)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	12.25	43.36	6.52	12.99	1.98	9617, 14578, 19644
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄]	(12.50)	(42.83)	(6.38)	(12.23)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ (ClO ₄) ₄	12.59	43.37	5.24	12.76	1.93	15873, 22727
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄]	(12.67)	(43.03)	(5.12)	(12.69)		
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄	12.05	42.38	5.77	11.59	2.00	16949, 21276
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄]						

Table 2(a). EPR spectral data of the complexes at LNT

Complexes	Temp. (K)	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ Cl ₄	77	2.4722	1.9823	2.1456
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ Cl ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ Cl ₄	77	2.4628	2.0129	2.1628
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ Cl ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ (NO ₃) ₄	77	2.4763	1.9987	2.1579
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (NO ₃) ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	77	2.4824	1.9785	2.1464
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (NO ₃) ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	77	2.4911	2.0255	2.1807
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	77	2.5201	2.0129	2.1817
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₁ (ClO ₄) ₄	77	2.5801	2.0575	2.2317
[C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄]				
(CuL) ₂ R ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄	77	2.5201	2.0510	2.2073
[C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄]				

Another parameter G is calculated by using the expression $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$. According to Chandra *et al.* if $G < 4$ indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. The calculated G values are larger than 4, suggesting that there is no interaction between the copper contents.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade, and procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All the solvents used were of standard/spectroscopic grade.

Synthesis of bis-macrocylic complexes :

To a solution of bridging diamine (0.0025 mol) (benzidine; 4,4'-diaminophenyl methane) as appropriate in methanol (20 mL), a solution of 36% formaldehyde (0.01 mol, 0.27 mL) in methanol (20 mL) was added. After 20 min a methanol solution of 1,3-diaminopropane (0.01 mol, 0.83 mL) in methanol (20 mL) was added. Finally a solution of metal salt of copper(II) (0.005 mol) and glyoxal (0.005 mol, 0.52 g) in methanol (20 mL) was added and the resulting mixture was stirred for *ca.* 16 h at room temperature. The brown solid product was filtered off, washed with methanol and dried over fused CaCl₂ in desiccators.

Physical measurements :

The C, H and N content were determined on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measure on the Elico (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄.5H₂O as a calibrant. IR

Table 2(b). EPR spectral data of the complexes at RT

Complexes	Temp. (K)	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	G
$(CuL)_2R_1Cl_4$ [C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ Cl ₄]	297	2.2266	2.0839	2.1314	2.7008
$(CuL)_2R_2Cl_4$ [C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ Cl ₄]	297	2.2343	2.0839	2.1340	2.7926
$(CuL)_2R_1(NO_3)_4$ [C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (NO ₃) ₄]	297	2.2122	2.0946	2.1338	2.2431
$(CuL)_2R_2(NO_3)_4$ [C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (NO ₃) ₄]	297	2.3055	2.0845	2.1581	3.6153
$(CuL)_2R_1(CH_3COO)_4$ [C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄]	297	2.3056	2.0906	2.1622	3.3730
$(CuL)_2R_2(CH_3COO)_4$ [C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄]	297	2.3042	2.0877	2.1598	3.4686
$(CuL)_2R_1(ClO_4)_4$ [C ₂₆ H ₄₄ N ₁₀ Cu ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄]	297	2.3056	2.0773	2.1533	3.9508
$(CuL)_2R_2(ClO_4)_4$ [C ₃₂ H ₄₈ N ₁₀ (Cu ₂ ClO ₄) ₄]	297	2.3043	2.0766	2.1573	3.9725

[(M(Me₂[15]aneN₃)₂R)Y₄]

where, X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and CH₃COO⁻; Y = ClO₄⁻

Fig. 1. Suggested structure of the complexes.

spectra (KBr) were recorded on FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer.

EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at room temperature and in the solution of DMF, at liquid nitrogen temperature on E₄-EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as a g-marker.

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